

Oxovanadium(IV,V) complexes of salicylidene-2-picoloyl hydrazone Schiff base and related ligands

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Abstract : Oxovanadium(IV,V) complexes having O₄N coordination environment have been synthesized in the solid state, formulated as M[VO₂(L/L'/L'')(H₂O)], where M = K or NH₄; H₂(L/L'/L'') is the Schiff base ligand, obtained by condensation of salicylaldehyde with 2-picoloyl (L), 2-quinoloyl (L'), 8-quinoloyl (L'') hydrazides. Dimeric complexes having the formulation [(VOL)₂μ-O] have also been synthesized. Both the salicylidene-picoloyl hydrazone and the salicylidene-2-quinoloyl hydrazone ligands, in their dideprotonated form, coordinate to both vanadium in its +4 and +5 state, through O, N, O donor atoms, while, the ligand H₂L'' will act as a NNO donor ligand. Thus, in the dioxo vanadium complexes with the ligands L and L', the central vanadium core will have the O₄N environment, which can be treated as a model to mimic the active site of vanadium haloperoxidases.

Keywords : Vanadium(IV,V), haloperoxidase, Schiff base, aroyl hydrazone.

The vanadate dependent haloperoxidases, the nitrogenases, other biologically active vanadium dependent compounds, their structural and other functional models has increased the interest in the coordination chemistry of vanadium¹⁻³. The vanadate in haloperoxidases, is present in trigonal pyramidal structure, in which the nitrogen atom of the histidine moiety is coordinated to vanadium^{4,5}, thus covalently linking the vanadate to the protein. Studies have been made in this respect on vanadium complexes with hydrazones⁶, amino acids⁷, and hydroxamates⁸, which are able to bind vanadium in both the +4 and +5 oxidation states. Structural studies have been reported^{9,10} on various types of oxovanadium complexes, e.g. [VO(OR)(HOR)L], [VO(OR)L], [(VOL)₂μ-O], [VOL(AA)], [VO₂L], where H₂L is a Schiff base hydrazone ligand and AA is a monobasic bidentate OO or ON donors. Since, aroyl hydrazones are of biochemical importance¹¹, the preparation and characterization of oxovanadium(IV,V) complexes with salicylidene-2-picoloyl hydrazone Schiff base and related ligands (Fig. 1), have been reported. The ligands as shown above (Fig. 1), contains five donor atoms, namely, the ring nitrogen, other two nitrogen of the hydrazone and the two oxygen of the phenol and the carbonyl group. All of them are not expected to act as donor simultaneously and even

R = 2-Pyridine; salicylidene-2-picoloyl hydrazone (H₂L)
R = 2-Quinoline; salicylidene-2-quinoloyl hydrazone (H₂L')
R = 8-Quinoline; salicylidene-8-quinoloyl hydrazone (H₂L'')

Fig. 1. Salicylidene hydrazone Schiff base ligands and their possible tautomeric forms.

quadridentate NONO coordination to a metal center is not possible due to ring strains. The ligands (H₂L) and (H₂L') might act¹²⁻¹⁴ as ONO donor in its keto form, not involving the ring nitrogen. However, in their enol form, it can act both as ONO donor as above and also as NNO donor involving the ring nitrogen atom. The 8-quinoloyl ligand (H₂L''), will act as a NNO donor, involving the ring nitrogen, both in its keto and enol form.

Experimental

The picoloyl, 2-quinoloyl and the 8-quinoloyl hydrazides were prepared by literature method¹⁵. The hydrazone Schiff bases, sal-2-picoloyl hydrazone, H₂L (light yellow; m.p. 175 °C), sal-2-quinoloyl hydrazone, H₂L'

(dirty yellow; m.p. 185 °C) and sal-8-quinoloyl hydrazone, H_2L'' (yellow; m.p. 146 °C) were prepared by condensing the salicylaldehyde with equimolar amounts of the respective hydrazides in ethanol over a steam bath. The CHN analyses of the ligands conform within 2% of their theoretical values. Ammonium vanadate, vanadium pentoxide, vanadyl sulfate were from Sigma, USA. The other chemicals used were of analytical grade. The details methodology for microanalyses, TGA and conductance measurements was discussed earlier^{16,17}. The UV-visible spectra were recorded either in a solid state mull or in methanol solution using Shimadzu 2401 PC, and the IR spectra in KBr pellets with Perkin-Elmer L 120-000A FT-IR spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out in our laboratory with a Gouy balance, using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as calibrant. The X-Band ESR spectra of the complexes were measured on a Bruker ESP X-Band, EPR spectrometer, using powdered samples at the microwave frequency 9.45 GHz, at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras.

Preparation of the complexes :

$K[VO_2L(H_2O)]$: Vanadium pentoxide (0.46 g, 5 mmol), dissolved in 10 ml aqueous KOH (0.29 g, 5 mmol) was added to a solution of the ligand L (1.2 g, 5 mmol) dissolved in 20 ml aqueous KOH (0.30 g, 5 mmol). The pH of the solution was brought to 7.5 by addition of 0.1 (N) NaOH solution. On stirring orange yellow crystals precipitated which was filtered off and dried in vacuum. The yield was 50 mg (30%); diamagnetic; decomposition temp. 110 °C; Anal. Found : V, 13.80; C, 42.00; H, 2.84; N, 11.18%. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{11}KN_3O_5V$ (FW, 379.1) : V, 13.45; C, 41.15; H, 2.90; N, 11.08%.

$NH_4[VO_2L(H_2O)]$: The compound was prepared as above except that NH_4VO_3 was taken in aqueous solution instead of vanadium pentoxide in KOH solution. NH_4VO_3 (0.58 g, 5 mmol) in 10 ml water solution was added to a solution of the ligand L (1.20 g, 5 mmol) in NaOH (0.40 g, 10 mmol) and pH of the solution was brought to 7.5 by adding 0.1 (N) NaOH solution. Orange yellow precipitate gradually separated out on stirring vigorously, which was filtered and dried in vacuum. The yield was 48 mg (30%); diamagnetic; decomposition temp. 100 °C. Anal. Found : V, 14.80; C, 44.02; H, 4.44; N, 14.88%. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{15}N_4O_5V$ (FW, 358.0) : V, 14.25; C, 43.57; H, 4.19; N, 15.64%.

$K[VO_2L'(H_2O)]$: This compound was prepared by following exactly the same procedure as adopted for the potassium salt above, except that 1.5 g (5 mmol) of L'

was taken instead of L. The bright yellow precipitate separated out. The yield was 49 mg (35%); diamagnetic; decomposition temp. 110 °C. Anal. Found : V, 12.00; C, 48.02; H, 3.11; N, 9.89%. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{13}KN_3O_5V$ (FW, 429.1) : V, 11.88; C, 47.54; H, 3.03; N, 9.79%.

$NH_4[VO_2L'(H_2O)]$: This compound was prepared adopting the same procedure as the above ammonium complex except that 1.5 g (5 mmol) of L' was used instead of L. The yield of the bright yellow compound was 70 mg (35%); diamagnetic; decomposition temp. 95 °C. Found : V, 13.00; C, 49.86; H, 4.19; N, 13.98%. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{17}N_4O_5V$ (FW, 408.0) : V, 12.50; C, 50.00; H, 4.17; N, 13.72%.

$[(VOL)_2\mu-O]$: NH_4VO_3 (0.58 g, 5 mmol) in 10 ml water solution was added to a solution of the ligand L (1.20 g, 5 mmol) in NaOH (0.40 g, 10 mmol). The resulting solution was stirred vigorously. The pH of the resulting solution remains around 4.5. Yellowish brown precipitate gradually separated out which was filtered and dried in vacuum. Yield : 1.2 g (60%); diamagnetic; decomposition temp. 150 °C. Found : V, 16.32; C, 49.86; H, 2.92; N, 13.98%. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{18}N_6O_7V_2$ (FW, 628.0) : V, 16.24; C, 49.68; H, 2.87; N, 13.38%.

$[VO(HL'')(H_2O)]SO_4$: An aqueous solution (10 ml) of $VOSO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$ (1.08 g, 5 mmol) was added to a solution of the ligand L'' (1.50 g, 5 mmol) in NaOH (0.40 g, 10 mmol). The pH of the solution was brought to 7.5 by adding 0.1 (N) NaOH solution, stirred vigorously. Greenish brown precipitate separated out immediately which was filtered and dried in vacuum yield : 1.05 g (45%); diamagnetic. Found : V, 11.00, C, 43.86; H, 3.02; N, 9.17%. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{17}N_4O_5V$ (FW, 408.0) : V, 10.83; C, 43.31; H, 2.97; N, 8.91%.

$[VOL(H_2O)]$: A solution of 1.2 g (5 mmol) of the ligand L in 10 ml aqueous methanol containing NaOH (0.4 g, 10 mmol) was added to 0.51 g (2.35 mmol) of $VOSO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$ in 10 ml of water. The pH of the resulting bluish green solution fell below 4.0, which was raised around 4.5 by dropwise addition of 0.1 (N) NaOH solution. Dark red precipitate appeared on stirring, separated by filtration, washed with methanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Yield : 37 mg (50%); paramagnetic ($\mu = 1.72$ B.M.). Found : C, 48.85; H, 3.29; N, 13.13%. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{11}N_3O_4V$ (FW, 324.0) : C, 48.15; H, 3.40; N, 12.96%.

$[VOL'(H_2O)]$: This dark red complex was isolated just by adopting the above procedure, taking 1.5 g, 5 mmol of L' instead of 1.2 g of L. The yield was 43 mg (50%); paramagnetic ($\mu = 1.65$ B.M.). Found : C, 55.15;

H, 3.79; N, 11.42%. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{13}N_3O_4V$ (FW, 374.0) : C, 54.55; H, 3.48; N, 11.23%.

Results and discussion

The compounds are non-hygroscopic, and are stable in air at room temperature. The molar conductance values of 10^{-3} (M) aqueous solution at 30°C of the potassium and ammonium salts of the complexes lie in between 110–125 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating the presence of 1 : 1 electrolytes. The salts of the complexes are fairly soluble in common solvents, such as, methanol, ethanol; DMF and DMSO. The dimeric complex of vanadium(V), containing the picoloyl ligand and the non-electrolytic complexes of vanadium(V) containing the picoloyl or the 2-quinoloyl ligands are sparingly soluble in the above solvents.

Thermogravimetric analyses :

The thermogravimetric analyses of all the compounds except that of the sulfate salt, containing the quinoloyl ligand were recorded. The important features of the TGA have been presented in Table 1. The first stage decomposition is complete around 180 °C for all the monomer complexes with a loss of one molecule of water. Hence, the water molecule is not strongly bound to vanadium; possibly, it is coordinated to vanadium in the trans position opposite to one of the double bonded oxygen atom. Then the dehydrated complexes become stable within the temperature range between 200° to 300 °C. It has been

possible to isolate the dehydrated complexes, $K[VO_2L]$, by pyrolysis at 160 °C. Further decomposition begins around 350 °C (Table 1) and the decomposition is complete around 750 °C with a horizontal corresponding to potassium metavanadate, KVO_3 residue. The ammonium salts of the complexes decompose in three stages (Table 1). The water molecule is released at the first stage as observed in the case of potassium salts. The decomposition

around 200 °C will be due to loss of NH_3 and $\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ from the anhydrous ammonium salts. These decompositions can be represented by the following reactions :

Finally, the decomposition is complete around 600 °C with a horizontal representing the V_2O_5 residue. However, it has not been possible to isolate the dimeric complex by pyrolysis of the ammonium salts at 250 °C.

The dimeric complex, $[(VOL)_2\mu-O]$ decomposes around 150 °C and become stable with a loss of $\frac{1}{2} O_2$ around 230 °C. This loss of oxygen is due to rapture of the oxygen bridge. The reaction may be represented as : $[(VOL)_2\mu-O] \rightarrow 2[VOL] + \frac{1}{2} O_2$. The product contains oxovanadium(IV) species. The above reaction sequence is an example of thermally induced reduction of vanadium from the +5 state to the +4 state. The above compound with a water molecule was isolated from vanadyl sulfate.

Table 1. Important features of thermogravimetric analysis

Compd.	Temp. (°C)	% Wt. Loss		Group lost	Residue	% Residue	
		obs.	(calcd.)			obs.	(calcd.)
$K[VO_2L(H_2O)]$	110–180	5.0	(4.8),	H_2O	$K[VO_2L]$	36.0	(36.4)
	330–750	64.0	(63.6)	L-1O	KVO_3		
$NH_4[VO_2L(H_2O)]$	110–180	5.0	(5.0),	H_2O	$NH_4[VO_2L]$	25.0	(25.4)
	200–320	12.0	(12.3),	$NH_3 + \frac{1}{2}H_2$	$\frac{1}{2}[V_2O_3L_2]$		
	350–600	75.0	(74.6)	L-1O	V_2O_5		
$K[VO_2L'(H_2O)]$	110–185	4.0	(4.2),	H_2O	$K[VO_2L']$	32.0	(32.2)
	340–750	69.0	(67.8)	L'-1O	KVO_3		
$NH_4[VO_2L'(H_2O)]$	105–180	4.5	(4.4),	H_2O	$NH_4[VO_2L']$	22.5	(22.3)
	210–330	11.0	(10.8),	$NH_3 + \frac{1}{2}H_2O$	$\frac{1}{2}[V_2O_3L_2]$		
	360–650	79.0	(77.7)	L'-1O	V_2O_5		
$[(VOL)_2\mu-O]$	150–230	2.6	(2.5)	$\frac{1}{2} O_2$	2[VOL]	29.0	(29.0)
	250–720	71.5	(71.0)	2L-3O	V_2O_5		
$[VOL(H_2O)]$	110–175	5.7	(5.5)	H_2O	[VOL]	28.0	(28.1)
	250–700	72.0	(71.9)	L-1½O	V_2O_5		
$[VOL'(H_2O)]$	120–185	5.0	(4.8)	H_2O	[VOL']	24.5	(24.3)
	260–730	76.0	(75.7)	L'-1½O	V_2O_5		

The oxovanadium(IV) complexes of the 2-picoloyl and the 2-quinoloyl ligands initially decompose around 110 °C. with the loss of one mole of water. The anhydrous complexes remain stable in between 200° to 250 °C, which gradually undergoes aerial oxidation and decompose to V₂O₅. The intermediate anhydrous complexes could not be isolated due to its poor stability.

Infrared spectra :

A broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is assigned due to the presence of coordinated water. The disappearance of the carbonyl amide band in the ligands around 1670 cm⁻¹ and appearance of new bands around 1200–1250 cm⁻¹ in both the picoloyl and the 2-quinoloyl complexes are due to enolization of the ligands and the coordination of enolic oxygen to vanadium. The ring nitrogen acts as a donor atom in the 8-quinoloyl complex, the (C=O) band is retained (1635 cm⁻¹) with a low frequency shift of 25 cm⁻¹. The ν(C=N) bands around 1610 cm⁻¹ of the ligands is shifted to low frequency in the complexes by 10–15 cm⁻¹, suggesting the coordination of the (C=N) group to vanadium through its nitrogen donor atom. This band splits into a doublet (1625 and 1595 cm⁻¹) in the dimeric complex, [(VOL)₂μ-O], due to the presence of the asymmetric oxygen bridge. The ν(N-N) around 980 cm⁻¹ shift to higher frequency in the complexes by around 40 cm⁻¹, due to the coordination of one nitrogen lone pair electrons to vanadium¹⁸. The two sharp bands in the region 900–950 cm⁻¹ for the dioxovanadium complexes, are assigned due to the presence of cis-VO₂⁺ unit⁶. The band at 870 cm⁻¹ due to [V-(μ-O)-V] vibration in the dimeric complex is due to the presence of asymmetric oxygen bridge in the complex^{19,20}.

UV-visible spectra :

The electronic absorption spectra of the picoloyl and the quinoloyl ligands were recorded in methanol. The absorption maxima with their extinction coefficients were presented in Table 2. The electronic absorption spectra of all the ligands and the picoloyl and the 2-quinoloyl complexes were also recorded in methanol. The UV spectra of the ligands shows three bands in the region 210–220 nm, 280–290 nm and 320–340 nm. The probable assignments of these bands are σ→σ*, π→π* and n→π* transitions respectively²¹. These bands are slightly shifted to lower wavelengths in the complexes. The weak shoulder associated with the second band in the dimeric oxovanadium(V) complex is not observed in the dioxovanadium(V) complexes. This shoulder may be due to hydrogen bonding and association, formed with the dimeric complex in solution. The oxovanadium(V) com-

plexes exhibit an intense to medium band in the visible region around 410 nm, due to charge transfer transitions, from the phenolate oxygen atom to an empty *d*-orbital of the vanadium atom. The oxovanadium(IV) complexes exhibit two weak bands around 660 and 530 nm. These weak bands may be assigned²² due to the transitions $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow e(d_{xz}, d_{yz})$ and $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_1(d_{x^2-y^2})$.

Table 2. Electronic absorption bands

Compd.	λ_{\max} (nm), ϵ (M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
H ₂ L (Sal-2-pico)	340 (16200), 290 (19040), 220 (25950)
H ₂ L' (Sal-2-quinol)	320 (16000), 280 (18900), 210 (25800)
H ₂ L'' (Sal-8-quinol)	325 (16100), 285 (18950), 210 (25910)
K[VO ₂ L(H ₂ O)]	405 (3760), 320 (6260), 280 (6800), 225 (14000)
NH ₄ [VO ₂ L(H ₂ O)]	400 (3030), 325 (5120), 280 (5410), 230 (10150)
K[VO ₂ L(H ₂ O)]	410 (6110), 315 (9650), 280 (10100), 235 (19850)
[(VOL) ₂ μ-O]	405, 320, 280 (sh), 225
[VO(III'')(H ₂ O)]SO ₄	390 (5990), 310 (9480), 290 (10800), 230 (21000)
[VOL(H ₂ O)]	660 (55), 530 (65), 405 (10500)
[VOL'(H ₂ O)]	665 (75), 525 (80), 410 (10800)

NMR spectra :

The ¹H spectra of the salicylidene-picoloyl hydrazone, its dioxovanadium and the dimeric complexes were recorded and presented in Table 3. The doublet and multiplet signals of the marked protons almost remain unchanged in the complexes with respect to free ligands. The azomethine (-CH=N) signal in the free ligand appears at δ 8.62 ppm, while the same in the dioxo complex appears at 9.03 ppm and in the dimeric complex at 9.02 ppm. This downfield shift of the azomethine signal with respect to the free ligand is due to the coordination of the nitrogen atom of the azomethine to the vanadium in both the complexes. The proton signals for the free ligand due to the phenolic-OH and the hydrazone-NH at 12.28 and 11.06 ppm respectively, disappear completely in the complexes. This disappearance of the -OH and the -NH signal is due to their coordination to vanadium through their oxygen and nitrogen respectively. The other aromatic protons in the free ligand as well as in the complexes, with slight shift in position, exhibit signals as given in the literature²³. Hence, the proton NMR signals also supports the dibasic tridentate coordination of the ligands and in line with the observations drawn from the infrared and electronic spectra of the complexes.

Reactions of the complex K[VO₂L(H₂O)] with H₂O₂ :
The ammonium salt of the dioxo complex, NH₄[VO₂L(H₂O)] reacts with 30% H₂O₂ in methanol in

Table 3. ¹H Chemical shift, δ ppm

Compd.	-OH	-NH	CH=N	H _a	H _d	H _e , H _b
H ₂ L	12.28	11.06	8.62	8.81 (d)	8.32 (d)	7.88 (m, br)
K[VO ₂ L(H ₂ O)]	-	-	9.00	8.70 (br)	8.24 (d)	7.80 (m, br)
[(VOL) ₂ μ-O]	-	-	9.02	8.78 (br)	8.28 (d)	7.85 (m, br)
Compd.	H ₄	H ₂	H ₁	H ₃		
H ₂ L	7.62 (d)	7.34 (m)	6.92 (m)	6.92 (m)		
K[VO ₂ L(H ₂ O)]	7.62 (d)	7.40 (m)	6.82 (m)	6.82 (m)		
[(VOL) ₂ μ-O]	7.64 (d)	7.44 (m)	6.88 (m)	6.88 (m)		

an ice bath to produce the corresponding oxoperoxo species in solution, as per the following equation :

The course of the reaction was monitored by the UV-Visible spectroscopy, by the addition of 0.1 ml portion of H₂O₂ to 5 ml 1 × 10⁻⁴ (M) solution in methanol of the ammonium salt. The 400 nm band is shifted to 415 nm, while the position of the bands at 325 and 230 nm remained unaltered. The band at 280 nm gradually disappeared. The new band at 415 nm remained constant for several hours. The rate of formation of the peroxo complex appears to be dependent on the amount of H₂O₂ added. It has been possible to isolate the mono peroxo complex at 10 °C, in the presence of excess H₂O₂. The isolated product shows an infrared absorption band at 895 cm⁻¹ due to peroxide stretching vibration, characteristics of the η²-coordination of the peroxo group²⁴. Besides, it shows the other IR active modes associated with the peroxide coordinated vanadium, at 580 and 740 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the symmetric and asymmetric vibrations of the coordinated peroxide group respectively. The isolated peroxo complex, NH₄[VO(O₂)L(H₂O)], is unstable and loses oxygen at room temperature. The compound becomes stable after 48 h. This stable compound on analysis found to correspond the dimeric complex. The conversion of the monoperoxo complex to dimeric complex may be represented as follows :

The magnetic moments of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes (Table 4), [VOL(H₂O)] and [VOL'(H₂O)] at 30 °C, was measured and found to be 1.72 and 1.65 B.M. respectively. These values correspond to the vanadium(IV) system consisting of d¹ electron.

EPR spectrum :

The EPR spectrum of the complexes [VOL(H₂O)] and [VOL'(H₂O)] at room temperature (23 °C) in CH₂Cl₂ solution, exhibits eight resonance lines having <g>, 1.975 and <A>, 84 × 10⁻⁴ cm⁻¹ for the former complex and <g>, 1.969 and <A>, 81 × 10⁻⁴ cm⁻¹ in accordance with the vanadium species having Schiff base ligand with ONO donor atoms^{25,26}. The above pattern results from the interaction of the vanadium single electron (d¹) in a d_{xy} orbital with the nuclear spin of the vanadium nucleus (⁵¹V, 99.76 atom %, I = 7/2). The isotropic EPR spectrum in CH₂Cl₂ solution is in consistent with the magnetic moment (Table 4) observed in the complexes.

Table 4. Magnetic moment of the complexes at 30 °C

Compd.	χ _g × 10 ⁶ cgs unit	χ _M × 10 ⁶ cgs unit	χ' _M × 10 ⁶ cgs unit	μ _{eff} B.M.
[VOL(H ₂ O)]	4.17	1351.04	1210.52	1.72
[VOL'(H ₂ O)]	3.45	1290.32	1114.00	1.65

Conclusion :

Hence from the above studies, it can be concluded that both the salicylidene-picoloyl hydrazone and the salicylidene-2-quinoloyl hydrazone ligands, in their

dideprotonated form, coordinate to both vanadium in its +4 and +5 state, through two oxygen, one each from the enolate, phenolate and the azomethine nitrogen group. The salicylidene-8-quinoloyl hydrazone (H_2L''), acts as a monobasic acid. In its monodeprotonated form, it acts as a tridentate donor ligand, coordinating to vanadium through the oxygen of the phenolate group, two nitrogen, one each from the azomethine group and the other from the quinoline ring. Therefore, the ligand H_2L'' will act as a NNO donor, whereas, the other two ligands, H_2L and H_2L' will act as an ONO donor. Thus, in the dioxo complexes, the central vanadium core will have the O_4N environment, which can be treated as a model to mimic the active site of vanadium haloperoxidases (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The proposed structure of the complex.

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